

GERMANY

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHING

GERMAN International Scientific Online
Conference:

«INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHING»

A collection of articles by Asian scholars

Issue 3, Part 1

Indexed databases:

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHING: a collection scientific works of the International scientific conference – Hamburg, Germany «AID», 2025. Issue 3 Part 1.

Languages of publication: English, Russian, German, Italian, Spanish

The collection consists of scientific research of scientists, graduate students and students who took part in the International Scientific online conference «**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHING**». Which took place in Hamburg in, 2025.

Conference proceedings are recommended for scientists and teachers in higher education establishments. They can be used in education, including the process of post - graduate teaching, preparation for obtain bachelors' and masters' degrees. The review of all articles was accomplished by experts, materials are according to authors copyright. The authors are responsible for content, researches results and errors.

© «AID», 2025

© Authors, 2025

SECTION 1. ARTICLES

1.	The Role Of Moral Education In Forming Patriotism And Social Activism In The Minds Of Young People Raxmatova Dinora Isomovna	5
2.	MS SQL SERVER: A MODERN DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM Zokirjonova Xushnozaxon Ulug'bek qizi	9
3.	SOCIAL MOTIVATION: ITS ROLE IN PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT Urazbayeva Yulduz Abdullayevna	12
4.	MANAGING ATTITUDE TOWARDS FAILURE: A PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR AMATEUR ATHLETES Raximov G'ulomjon Davronbekovich	16
5.	THE PRINCIPLE OF PROPERTY INVIOABILITY IN PUBLIC INTERNATIONAL LAW: EVOLUTION AND CURRENT STATE Bositkhon Akmalkhonov	20
6.	MICROCIRCULATION: PHYSIOLOGY, PATHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS, AND CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS Mansurova Dilorom Aslonovna	28
7.	NEURAL NETWORKS AND GENETIC ALGORITHMS Tojimatov Isroiljon Nurmatovich	35
8.	KNOWLEDGE REPOSITORY. STRUCTURE OF A KNOWLEDGE REPOSITORY Israil Tojimatov Nurmatovich , Sharofutdinov Iqboljon	40
9.	THE STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION, CULTURE, AND SPIRITUALITY IN NEW UZBEKISTAN Sadikova Kamila Rustamovna	48
10.	SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO EDUCATION QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS Narimanova Saida Narimon qizi	52
11.	HISTORICAL SECRETS OF THE ERA OF ABDULHAMID KHAN II OLTIYEV ASIRBEK RO'ZIQUL O'G'LI	59
12.	ЖЕНЩИНЫ В ДИПЛОМАТИИ: РАЗВИТИЕ ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАВЕНСТВА В МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЯХ Каримов Шохрухбек Абдусатторови	64
13.	БУДУЩЕЕ ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО СОЮЗА В УСЛОВИЯХ КРИЗИСА И ВНУТРЕННИХ ПРОТИВОРЕЧИЙ Каримов Шохрухбек Абдусатторович	68
14.	WOMEN IN DIPLOMACY: DEVELOPING GENDER EQUALITY IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS Gomez Elena	74

SOCIAL MOTIVATION: ITS ROLE IN PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT**Urazbayeva Yulduz Abdullayevna**

Doctor of Philosophy in Psychology (PhD)

Teacher of the Department of Psychology and Medicine, Mamun University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16732915>

Abstract: This thesis analyzes the role and importance of social motivation in the development of a person. It highlights how factors such as the social environment, the assessment of others, and the desire to achieve social status shape a person's internal motivation, its impact on the processes of self-awareness, self-improvement, and goal-directedness. It also analyzes how social motivation is reflected in education, labor activity, social adaptation, and psychological well-being on a scientific and theoretical basis. The thesis is written on the basis of psychological, pedagogical, and sociological approaches, and special attention is paid to the social components of motivation in personal development.

Keywords: social motivation, personal development, social environment, motivation, motivational factors, personal growth, social influence, psychological development.

Introduction.

As long as a person lives in society, he is never formed in isolation. The social consciousness, character, value system, and outlook on life of each person are influenced by the social environment. This environment is especially manifested as an important factor in the individual's actions, aspirations and self-expression. In this system of factors, social motivation plays a central role. Social motivation is manifested as a force that stimulates a person's internal needs, such as finding a position in society, comparing oneself with others, striving for a positive assessment, and achieving social recognition.

If motivation in a general sense is an internal force that encourages action, then social motivation is a mental and volitional state formed through a person's attitude towards the people around him, social groups, values and norms. For example, if a child carefully prepares for a lesson in the hope of hearing praise from his parents or teacher, this is the result of his social motivation. Or if a young man strives for professional development in order to gain prestige in society, this is also an example of social motivation.

The issue of motivation is widely studied in modern psychology, but the unique role of social motivation in the development of the individual has not yet been fully revealed. In this regard, it is of great importance to identify various forms and sources of motivation, analyze them in connection with the stages of individual development, and develop mechanisms for the formation of healthy social motivation, especially in the education system and among young people.

This thesis analyzes the essence of social motivation, its formation mechanisms, its

impact on personal development, and ways to effectively manage it on a scientific basis. The goal is to provide theoretical and practical justification for the possibility of a positive impact on human development through social factors.

Theoretical basis.

The concept of social motivation is considered a complex, multifaceted phenomenon in psychology and pedagogy. This concept is closely related to such needs as self-awareness in society, sensitivity to the assessment of others, and the desire to achieve social status. In determining the theoretical foundations of social motivation, it is important to rely on the views of classical psychologists and modern motivation theorists.

First of all, A. Maslow's theory of the hierarchy of needs considers the gradual formation of motivation. According to him, social needs - namely, friendship, recognition and respect - are an important stage before a person's self-expression. By satisfying his social needs, a person feels like a full-fledged member of society. This situation gives a strong internal impetus to the development of the individual.

Also, supporters of the sociocultural approach, such as L.S. Vygotsky and A.N. Leontyev, emphasize the social origin of motivation. In their opinion, human behavior and activity are formed by social conditions, cultural traditions and interpersonal relationships. Motivation, viewed from this perspective, is a dynamic process that arises not only from individual internal needs, but also under the influence of social experience and values.

In modern research, social motivation is directly related to a person's psychological well-being, level of self-awareness, determination to set personal and professional goals and achieve them. For example, according to Ryan and Deci's self-determination theory, people are motivated when they feel autonomy, competence, and social connectedness in their activities. It is this connectedness—that is, positive, supportive relationships with other people—that is, the basis of social motivation.

Social motivation is also formed in connection with social roles, statuses, and stereotypes. A person tries to fulfill the roles expected of him or her and strives to meet the expectations of society. This, on the one hand, can strengthen personal aspirations, but on the other hand, it can lead to unfavorable social pressures or behavioral adaptation. The above theoretical views show that social motivation serves as a powerful internal driving force in the development of a person. To form, manage and positively direct it, conscious approaches are necessary in education, upbringing and family environment. In particular, socially stimulating the younger generation, attracting them to a positive motivational environment is an important guarantee of sustainable personal development.

Analytical discussion:

Social motivation is an important psychological factor at the heart of personal

development. This type of motivation is manifested through a person's sense of belonging to society, involvement in social relations, as well as sensitivity to social assessments. Social motivation often plays a leading role in a person's actions, but this process can also take on a complex and contradictory character.

First of all, the analysis shows that social motivation encourages a person to act in response to external social influences. For example, a child wants to earn the recognition of his parents or teacher by getting high marks at school. Or, an adult works on himself to gain prestige and attention in society, strives to be socially active. In this case, motivation is formed through the interaction between internal needs and external social evaluation. However, there are also negative aspects of social motivation. Excessive dependence on social evaluations can limit a person's ability to think independently and make individual decisions. This situation, especially in young people, leads to the formation of "doing what the majority says," that is, conformist behavior. Comparing oneself with others, the desire to achieve ideal social images can in some cases cause self-doubt, psychological pressure or stress. Nevertheless, positive changes in a person occur only if social motivation is directed correctly. If social incentives (praise, recognition, status in society) correspond to the abilities, work, and individual approaches of the person, then such motivation leads to self-development. Otherwise, misjudged or denied social needs will cause negative traits in the individual, such as discontent, indifference, passivity, or aggression. Another important aspect of the discussion is that social motivation is expressed differently depending on the age. While children need social stimulation more in an external form (appreciation, gifts, attention), for adolescents, friends and status in the community are important. Adults are motivated by social self-realization, that is, professional growth, gaining prestige, and achieving goals. Thus, social motivation is a constantly developing and changing factor in accordance with the individual's life stages.

From this perspective, in order to strengthen social motivation, a positive, encouraging, trusting and supportive environment should be created in the education system, family environment and society towards the individual. Social motivation, when properly formed, allows the individual to think creatively, develop himself, establish strong social relationships and adapt to a healthy society.

Conclusion.

Based on the theoretical analysis and analytical discussions conducted above, it can be concluded that social motivation is an integral part of personal development, which plays an important role in a person's self-awareness, establishing social relationships with others, striving for goals and involvement in social activities. Social motivation is directly related to the social needs of the individual - recognition, respect, belonging, status - and when these needs are satisfied, a person develops a healthy self-esteem, a desire for positive changes and a sense of satisfaction with life.

Strong and correct formation of social motivation encourages a person to be active, work on himself, grow professionally and morally. However, misdirected or denied social motivation can cause negative psychological states in a person, conformism, internal dissatisfaction, lack of self-confidence or withdrawal from social activity. Therefore, managing social motivation and shaping it in a positive direction, especially in education and upbringing systems, remains one of the priority tasks.

The study shows that the effective effect of social motivation is achieved not only by external incentives (praise, assessment, recognition), but also by recognizing the internal needs and dignity of the individual, seeing him as an important person in society. When each person feels himself a valued, necessary, useful member of society, his motivation also serves social stability. Therefore, the formation of social motivation and its management in the direction of personal development is of urgent importance not only for the individual, but also for the intellectual, spiritual and economic development of society. In this process, the family, educational institutions, the media and the general public should work together to form positive social motivation in each person.

List of used literature:

1. Maslow A. Motivation and personality / Trans. from English. – St. Petersburg: Eurasia, 1999. – 352 p.
2. Vygotsky L.S. Psychology of human development. – Moscow: Smysl, 2005. – 512 p.
3. Leontiev A.N. Activity. Consciousness. Personality. – Moscow: Politizdat, 1977. – 304 p.
4. Ryan R., Desi E. Theory of self-determination and motivation of behavior // Psychological journal. – 2000. – Vol. 21, No. 5. – P. 55–67.
5. Nazarova F.N. Psychology of motivation of students' educational activities. – T.: Science and technology, 2019. – 184 p.
6. Karimov A.A. Personality psychology. – Tashkent: Teacher, 2021. – 220 p.
7. Saydaliyev M. Fundamentals of social psychology. – Tashkent: NMIU "Ma'naviyat", 2018. – 198 p.
8. Jalolov J. Pedagogical technologies. – Tashkent: Science, 2012. – 264 p.